

Integrating enriched case data from national laboratory testing with population-based case-control analyses: a novel statistical likelihood-ratio methodology for PS4 applied to 325,345 breast cancer cases and 671,006 controls

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Abstract (200 words)

Background: For many evidence criteria within v3.0 of the ACMG/AMP guidelines, methodologies have been developed to empower their use outside categorical evidence strengths. However, no such methodology has been established for case-control data (PS4). With the release of large-scale unselected case-control datasets and expansion of nationally-collected laboratory datasets enriched for pathogenic variant carriers, there is potential to combine datasets across ascertainment contexts in a more quantitative manner using novel likelihood ratio tools.

Methods: Using our published PS4-LR-Calculator, we calculated a combined log likelihood ratio (PS4-LLR) across five datasets (three unselected, and two enriched), and estimated enrichment of pathogenic variants in clinically-ascertained laboratory data using truncating variant prevalence.

Results: Data were combined for 10,694 missense variants from 325,345 female breast cancer patients and 671,006 controls of Western European ancestry for five breast cancer susceptibility genes (*BRCA1*, *BRCA2*, *PALB2*, *ATM*, *CHEK2*). A combined LLR was produced for 4,563 missense variants; 922 variants received evidence towards pathogenicity ($LLR \geq 1$), and 3,188 received evidence towards benignity ($LLR \leq -1$).

Conclusion: This flexible, variant-level methodology combines nationally-collected 'enriched' datasets with unselected case-control cohorts, expanding the available information for case-control analysis, boosting power for existing analyses and enabling further exploration of variants in atypical penetrance scenarios.

Introduction (663)

The observation of a higher frequency of a variant of interest in cases of a given disease than in controls is one of the most fundamental pieces of evidence by which it can be inferred that the variant is disease-associated and thus pathogenic. This evidence is especially valuable for missense variants for which, unlike protein truncating variants, the prior probability of pathogenicity is low. And while individually rare, missense variants are in aggregate a common occurrence in diagnostic laboratories and frequently classified as variants of uncertain significance (VUS).

In the ACMG/AMP v3.0 framework, it was stipulated that case-control data of appropriate statistical significance ($p < 0.05$) and appropriate effect size ($OR \geq 5$) could be awarded 'strong' evidence (PS4)¹. Unlike other evidence codes in the ACMG/AMP v3.0 framework, there was no subsequent specification by the ClinGen Sequence Variant Interpretation Group (SVI) of how more graded evidence might be awarded or how this frequentist threshold should be translated across to the Bayesian framework they subsequently advocated in 2019 and which will be used across the v4.0 framework update due for release in 2026².

To address this, we devised a method using Gaussian adaptive quadrature (the PS4-LR-Calculator), by which, for a given set of observations of variant in those with disease and those without disease, the likelihood that the variant is associated with disease is compared to the likelihood that the variant is non-associated, given a pre-specified target odds ratio³. This generates a likelihood ratio; the log (to base 2.08) of the likelihood ratio (LLR) can readily be applied as 'evidence points' within the ACMG/AMP Bayesian framework⁴. LLRs can be readily summed across different case-control datasets, to maximise the evidence available for classification of a given variant. This type of approach has previously been illustrated in a

recent analysis of variants in *BRCA1* and *BRCA2* in 96,691 unselected population-based cases of breast cancer and 302,116 controls from three case-control research datasets: BRIDGES, CARRIERS and UK Biobank⁵⁻⁸.

However, there are a wealth of variant data from clinical diagnostic testing not captured when restricting to formal case-control research datasets. These clinical datasets firstly lack controls, and secondly include cases of diseases selected through application of eligibility criteria for testing. This unquantified level of “enrichment”, whilst potentially powerful in regard of variant interpretation, renders it challenging to then combine variant association metrics for these clinically-ascertained cases with those from population-based unselected breast cancer cases.

An additional emergent consideration is disease penetrance, which the PS4-LR-Calculator methodology is well-placed to address on account of its ability to flexibly accommodate any user-specified target odds ratio. Whilst the field of breast cancer susceptibility is ahead of most disease communities in having defined thresholds for defining genes of high penetrance ($OR \geq 4$, such as *BRCA1*, *BRCA2* and *PALB2*) and for genes of moderate penetrance ($OR \geq 2$, such as *CHEK2* and *ATM*), it is increasingly recognised that some variants in high penetrance genes are of reduced (moderate) penetrance and that some variants in moderate penetrance genes are of elevated (high) penetrance⁹⁻¹³. This poses concomitant challenges in applying case-control data for variant classification.

Using the PS4-LR-Calculator, we have developed a case-control methodology for leveraging enriched nationally-collected breast cancer datasets in combination with unselected disease series. We present here combination of a clinical series of 187,642 enriched breast cases tested by Ambry, USA (analysed against 175,054 ancestry-matched controls from gnomAD v4.1.0¹⁴), a clinical series of 44,917 enriched breast cases tested by NHS laboratories in the UK (analysed against 297,141 ancestry-matched controls from UK Biobank) and 92,786 unselected breast cancer cases and 198,811 controls from BRIDGES, CARRIERS and UK Biobank. In total, we analysed a combined dataset of 325,345 white female breast cancer cases and 671,006 non-breast cancer/population controls for rare variants in *BRCA1*, *BRCA2*, *PALB2*, *CHEK2* and *ATM*, making this, to our knowledge, the largest case-control analysis of these genes to date. We have also investigated application of case-control data under reduced penetrance hypotheses for variants in genes of high penetrance, and high penetrance hypotheses for variants in genes of moderate penetrance.

Methods (769)

Patients and data sources

Data was obtained for the *BRCA1*, *BRCA2*, *PALB2*, *ATM* and *CHEK2* genes from three population-based unselected breast cancer genetic testing studies (CARRIERS⁷, UK Biobank⁸, and 30 unselected studies from BRIDGES⁶) and from two enriched laboratory datasets (NDRS-UK, Ambry) (Table 1, Supplementary Methods)). We also included 175,053 non-UK Biobank non-Finnish European individuals from gnomAD v4.1.0 as population controls¹⁴ (Figure 1).

Dataset	Genes	Ascertainment	Cases	Controls	Location	Cancer phenotype	Sex (cases)	Sex (controls)	Ancestry
UK Biobank	<i>ATM</i> , <i>BRCA1</i> , <i>BRCA2</i> , <i>CHEK2</i> , <i>PALB2</i>	Unselected	18,477	419,373	UK	Breast	Female	Female+ Male	White
CARRIERS	<i>ATM</i> , <i>BRCA1</i> , <i>BRCA2</i> , <i>CHEK2</i> , <i>PALB2</i>	Unselected	32,247	32,544	USA	Breast	Female	Female	Non-Hispanic White
BRIDGES	<i>ATM</i> , <i>BRCA1</i> , <i>BRCA2</i> , <i>CHEK2</i> , <i>PALB2</i>	Unselected	42,062	44,035	Europe	Breast	Female	Female	European
Ambry	<i>ATM</i> , <i>BRCA1</i> , <i>BRCA2</i> , <i>CHEK2</i> , <i>PALB2</i>	Clinical	187,642	NA	USA	Breast	Female	NA	White
NDRS-UK	<i>BRCA1</i> , <i>BRCA2</i>	Clinical	44,917	NA	UK	Breast	Female	NA	White
gnomAD v4.1.0	<i>ATM</i> , <i>BRCA1</i> , <i>BRCA2</i> , <i>CHEK2</i> , <i>PALB2</i>	Population	NA	175,054	Global	NA	NA	Female+ Male	Non-Finnish European

Table 1: Summary of datasets included in analysis.

Figure 1: Flowchart of data collected and filtering steps employed to calculate the combined PS4-LLR

Protein-truncating variants (PTVs) were defined as variants not in the final exon with one of the following variant effect consequences, annotated using Ensembl VEP¹⁵ (v112): "stop_gained", "splice_acceptor_variant", "splice_donor_variant", "frameshift_variant", "start_loss". Missense variants were defined as variants with a VEP consequence of "missense". All variant nomenclature was verified using VariantValidator^{16,17}.

For all datasets, variants which met the criteria for BA1 (allele frequency exceeding maximum tolerated allele frequency, MTAf) in gnomAD v4.1.0 were removed according to the MTAfs defined by the respective variant curation expert group (VCEP): *BRCA1*, 0.000868¹³; *BRCA2*, 0.000906¹³; *PALB2*, 0.00118¹⁸; *ATM*, 0.00625¹⁹; *CHEK2*, 0.00625¹⁹.

Case-control analysis

For each variant, the LR from each individual study was calculated using the PS4-LR-Calc as published³; briefly, the calculator uses the observed frequency of a variant in both cases and controls to form two starting hypotheses: the hypothesis of association (that the underlying odds ratio indicates pathogenicity, the default threshold being more than 5), hereafter 'target odds of association', and the hypothesis of non-association (that the underlying odds indicate benignity, the default threshold being less than 1). The likelihood of each competing hypothesis being true is modelled by a binomial distribution, and the summed likelihood of each hypothesis compared to reach the final LR.

Initial review and analysis revealed the need for further rules to appropriately apply case-control evidence when using PS4-LR-Calc. These rules include removal of singleton observations, exclusion of benign evidence from datasets where benign variants were underreported, and calculation of an Enrichment Factor (EF) for enriched laboratory datasets (Supplementary Methods).

An observed odds ratio (OR), 95% confidence intervals, and Fisher's exact p-value were also calculated for each variant in each dataset. Additional meta-analysis was carried out for the OR calculated for the three unselected datasets on a per-variant basis, using a fixed-effect inverse-variance weighted approach (Supplementary Methods).

All analyses were performed using R version 4.3.0 (2023-04-21 ucrt) and R Studio version 2025.05.1 Build 513. Kruskal-Wallis and Dunn test performed using the rstatix package for R. All plots were created using the ggplot2, ggpubr, and ggsankey packages for R.

Combined LR calculation

Per-variant LR from each study were combined as follows:

$$TotLR = LR_1 \times LR_2 \times LR_3 \dots \times LR_n$$

using data from n datasets for which an LR could be calculated. TotLR were log transformed (base 2.08) as per the Tavtigian *et al.* scaled point system to assess potential evidence strengths applicable for variant classification^{2,4}. The default target odds of association used was 4 for high-penetrance genes (*BRCA1*, *BRCA2*, *PALB2*), and 2 for moderate penetrance genes (*ATM*, *CHEK2*), as per published recommendations for high increased risk and moderate increased risk for breast cancer relative to the general population risk^{12,13}.

Concordance of results with other data

Concordance of case-control evidence was measured against 1 star missense classifications from ClinVar (data release 01 June 2025)²⁰. For *BRCA1* and *BRCA2* variants, case-control evidence was compared against evidence applicable under functional (PS3/BS3) and predictive (PP3/BP4) criteria recommended by the ClinGen ENIGMA *BRCA1* and *BRCA2*

Reinterpretation of missense VUS

Missense variants with classifications of VUS or conflicting interpretations were identified from ClinVar, as described above. *BRCA1* and *BRCA2* variants were annotated with case-control evidence calculated using a target $OR \geq 4$.

Using additional annotations following the ClinGen ENIGMA *BRCA1* and *BRCA2* Guidelines as part of automated classification, variants with results from high-throughput functional assays attained strong evidence for PS3 or BS3 (Supplementary Methods). Variants in potentially clinically important functional domains with data from BayesDel²¹ and SpliceAI²² exceeding recommended thresholds attained supporting evidence for PP3 or BP4 (Supplementary Methods). BA1 and BS1 were not used to avoid double-counting of population data already used in calculation of PS4-LLR.

Penetrance investigation

For high-penetrance genes (*BRCA1*, *BRCA2*, and *PALB2*), four criteria were defined to identify potentially reduced penetrance variants when comparing standard ($OR \geq 4$) to reduced penetrance ($OR \geq 2$) target odds of association:

- Evidence strength changes direction (Any benign to Any pathogenic)
- Loses benign evidence (Benign Moderate or stronger to No Evidence)
- Gains pathogenic evidence (No evidence to Pathogenic Moderate or stronger)
- Substantially strengthens weakly pathogenic evidence (Pathogenic Moderate to Very Strong, or Pathogenic Supporting to Strong or Very Strong)

For any criterion, a minimum change of two evidence strength categories was required (e.g. a change of supporting to moderate would not meet any criterion).

For moderate-penetrance genes (*ATM*, *CHEK2*), we investigated high-penetrance variants by identifying variants which retained at least strong pathogenic evidence at $OR \geq 4$.

Results (1373)

Dataset enrichment

Enrichment of pathogenic variants was estimated by comparing per-gene allele frequency of protein-truncating variants (PTV) in enriched cases against an average allele frequency of PTVs in unselected cases. The UK laboratory dataset was found to be 4.87 times enriched for *BRCA1* PTVs and 3.94 times enriched for *BRCA2* PTVs. The Ambry dataset was also enriched to a lesser extent; all genes were between 1.82-2.65 times enriched in the Ambry dataset (Table 2, Table S1).

Enriched dataset	Gene	PTV carriers (Enriched cases)	Total tested (Enriched cases)	Allele Frequency (Enriched cases)	PTV carriers (Unselected Cases)	Total tested (Unselected Cases)	Allele Frequency (Unselected Cases)	Enrichment Factor (95% CI)
NDRS-UK	<i>BRCA1</i>	1606	44917	0.036	685	93377	0.007	4.87 (4.46-5.33)
	<i>BRCA2</i>	2165	44917	0.048	1141	93377	0.012	3.94 (3.67-4.23)
Ambry	<i>BRCA1</i>	3642	187642	0.019	685	93377	0.007	2.65 (2.44-2.87)
	<i>BRCA2</i>	5688	187642	0.030	1141	93377	0.012	2.48 (2.33-2.64)
	<i>PALB2</i>	1646	187642	0.009	423	93377	0.005	1.94

								(1.74-2.15)
	<i>ATM</i>	2186	187642	0.012	535	93377	0.006	2.03 (1.85-2.23)
	<i>CHEK2</i>	4539	187642	0.024	1243	93377	0.013	1.82 (1.71-1.93)

Table 2: Per-gene enrichment factors calculated by comparison of truncating variant prevalence in cases in unselected breast cancer datasets and enriched laboratory datasets. NDRS-UK=National Disease Registration Service, UK; PTV=Protein Truncating Variant; CI=Confidence Interval.

Results from PS4-LLR analyses of the combined dataset

In total, 13,829 rare PTV and missense variants in five genes were identified across the five datasets (in 325,345 female breast cancer cases and 671,006 controls) (Table S2).

Of 3,135 rare PTVs, 45% (1,423/3,135) were excluded from analysis due to violating at least one variant inclusion rule (Supplementary Methods) of which 99.6% (1,415/1,423) were due to being singleton observations (Table S3). Of the remaining 1,712 variants, 65% (1,120/1,712) attained PS4-LLR evidence towards pathogenicity (312, 168, 276, and 364 at supporting, moderate, strong, or very strong PS4-LLR respectively), and 15% (262/1,712) attained evidence towards benignity (45, 90, 73, and 54 at supporting, moderate, strong, or very strong respectively).

Of 10,694 rare missense variants, 57% (6,131/10,694) were excluded from analysis, 98.3% (6,027/6,131) due to being singleton observations (Table S4). Of the remaining 4,563 missense variants, 20% (922/4,563) attained PS4-LLR evidence towards pathogenicity (LLR \geq 1), 70% (3,188/4,563) attained PS4-LLR evidence towards benignity (LLR \leq -1) and 10% (453/4,563) attained no evidence towards pathogenicity/benignity.

Considering the ACMG/AMP v3.0 evidence categories of supporting, moderate, strong, very strong, 84% (473/565) of *BRCA1* missense variants with benign evidence (LLR \leq -1) attained at least strong evidence (LLR \leq -4), while 43% (55/127) of *BRCA1* variants with pathogenic evidence (LLR \geq 1) attained at least strong evidence (LLR \geq 4). Similarly, for *BRCA2*, 81% (918/1,128) and 40% (83/207) variants reached at least strong evidence towards benignity and pathogenicity respectively. By comparison, far fewer *PALB2* variants attained strong/very strong pathogenic evidence (13% (11/84), Table 3).

For moderate penetrance genes, assessed against a target of OR of 2, 23% (85/364) and 61% (535/879) of *ATM* variants with evidence towards pathogenicity and benignity respectively attained at least strong evidence. For *CHEK2*, the proportion of variants which attained evidence towards pathogenicity was higher than any other gene at 37% (140/376); of these, 36% (51/140) attained at least strong evidence.

	TOTAL VARIANTS	Any pathogenic evidence (% total)	No evidence (% total)	Any benign evidence (% total)	PS4-LLR Evidence towards pathogenicity (LLR \geq 1)				PS4-LLR Evidence towards benignity (LLR \leq -1)			
					VSTR	STR	MOD	SUP	SUP	MOD	STR	VSTR
					<i>BRCA1</i>	783	127 (16)	91 (12)	565 (72)	25	30	28
<i>BRCA2</i>	1489	207 (14)	154 (10)	1128 (76)	27	56	57	67	54	156	322	596
<i>PALB2</i>	540	84 (16)	35 (6)	421 (78)	5	6	35	38	18	88	103	212
<i>ATM</i>	1375	364 (26)	132 (10)	879 (64)	24	61	125	154	90	254	289	246

<i>CHEK2</i>	376	140 (37)	41 (11)	195 (52)	25	26	29	60	13	63	66	53
TOTAL	4563	922 (20)	453 (10)	3188 (70)	106	179	274	363	195	633	928	1432

Table 3: Overview of evidence attained for 4,563 rare missense variants included in the combined dataset. Target odds of association were set at $OR \geq 4$ for *BRCA1*, *BRCA2*, and *PALB2*, and $OR \geq 2$ for *ATM* and *CHEK2*.

Examining the PS4-LLR as a continuous score, not divided into ACMG/AMP v.3.0 categories, evidence ranged from LLR of +161 to -1016 across all genes, with *PALB2* having the narrowest evidence range (+16 to -177). Extreme PS4-LLRs towards pathogenicity were observed for relatively frequent well-established pathogenic variants; notably, *BRCA1*: c.181T>G (p.C61G) (+161), *BRCA2*: c.7988A>T (p.E2663V) (+136), c.8167G>C (p.D2723H) (+120), *ATM*: c.7271T>G (p.V2424G) (+65) (see Discussion).

Mean PS4-LLR for each gene was negative (i.e. $LLR < 0$), demonstrating that overall, as might be anticipated, more evidence was attained by variants towards benignity than pathogenicity (Figure 2). Mean PS4-LLR for *BRCA1*, *BRCA2*, and *PALB2* were -12.4, -12.3, and -10.2. Comparing distributions of PS4-LLR for each gene, average PS4-LLR for *ATM* and *CHEK2* differed significantly from *BRCA1*, *BRCA2*, and *PALB2* (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Boxplot of PS4-LLR evidence assigned for 4,563 rare missense variants included in the combined dataset. Each dot represents a single variant. Red dashed line represents 0 evidence points attained. For 30 variants with negative PS4-LLR more extreme than -160, LLR was set to a maximum limit of -160. Statistically significant differences between average LLR for each gene are displayed (Kruskal-Wallis rank sum: $p\text{-value} = 9.25 \times 10^{-62}$, Bonferroni-adjusted $p\text{-value}$ threshold for significance = 0.005)

Concordance with ClinVar classifications

Of the total of 26,629 missense variants listed in ClinVar for *BRCA1*, *BRCA2*, *PALB2*, *CHEK2* and *ATM* and reported with at least 1 star, 1,214 were reported as Pathogenic, Likely Pathogenic, Likely Benign, or Benign, and 25,415 variants were reported as VUS or with

conflicting classifications. 17% (4,441/26,629) of missense variants in ClinVar have corresponding data in our final combined dataset; 27% (330/1,214) of variants with at least 1 star, and 16% (4,111/25,415) of VUS or conflicting variants.

For the 330 classified variants with at least 1 star, 72% (84/116) of ClinVar P/LP classified variants attained PS4-LLR towards pathogenicity ($LLR \geq 1$), with 7% (8/116) attaining no points and 21% (24/116), attaining PS4-LLR points towards benignity with 2, 8, 9, and 5 variants in the supporting, moderate, strong, very strong range respectively. 89% (190/214) of ClinVar B/LB classified variants attained PS4-LLR towards benignity ($LLR \leq -1$), with 5% (11/214) attaining no points and 6% (13/214) attaining PS4-LLR towards pathogenicity with 5, 4, 3, and 1 variants respectively in the supporting, moderate, strong, very strong range (Figure 3, Table S5).

Figure 3: 330 missense variants across five genes with PS4-LLR between 200 and -200 classified in ClinVar as either pathogenic, likely pathogenic, likely benign, or benign with at least one star. 17 variants with a $PS4-LLR \leq -200$ not depicted; all 17 of these variants were classified as Benign with 3* expert panel classifications. PS4-LLR was calculated using $OR \geq 4$ for BRCA1, BRCA2, and PALB2, and $OR \geq 2$ for ATM and CHEK2.

To minimise impact of single submitters to ClinVar, which may be historic and/or erroneous, we repeated this analysis restricting inclusion of ClinVar records to those with at least 2 stars (multiple lab submissions and/or expert panel classifications) (Figure S2). 143 *BRCA1* and 125 *BRCA2* variants met this criteria. Of these 268 variants, 80% (59/74) of ClinVar 2* pathogenic variants with PS4-LLR attained concordant evidence towards pathogenicity, with 15% (11/74) attaining PS4-LLR towards benignity with 0, 3, 6, and 2 in the supporting,

moderate, strong, very strong range respectively. 90% (174/194) benign variants with PS4-LLR attained concordant evidence towards benignity, with 5% (10/194) attaining PS4-EPs towards pathogenicity with 4, 2, 3, and 1 respectively in the supporting, moderate, strong, very strong range.

Concordance with functional data and in silico predictions

Of 1,929 *BRCA1/BRCA2* variants with a VUS or conflicting classification in ClinVar, 248 had at least supporting evidence from both functional data and case-control data (152 in *BRCA1* and 96 in *BRCA2*). For 87% (216/248), the functional evidence was concordant with the direction of evidence from case-control data (87% (132/152) in *BRCA1* and 88% (84/96) in *BRCA2*). There were 23 discordant variants with functional evidence indicating neutrality, with 7, 4, 10, and 2 respectively attaining PS4-LLR evidence towards pathogenicity in the supporting, moderate, strong, very strong range. There were 9 discordant variants with functional evidence of deleteriousness, with 0, 3, 3, and 3 respectively attaining PS4-LLR evidence towards benignity in the supporting, moderate, strong, very strong range.

For the 331 *BRCA1/BRCA2* variants with at least supporting evidence from both in silico predictive tools (BayesDel, SpliceAI) and case-control data, (87 in *BRCA1* and 244 in *BRCA2*), 68% (251/371) had predictive evidence that was concordant with the direction of evidence from case-control data (66% (57/87) in *BRCA1* and 75% (184/244) in *BRCA2*). There were 38 discordant variants with predictive evidence indicating neutrality, of which 12, 13, 9, and 4 respectively attained PS4-LLR towards pathogenicity in the supporting, moderate, strong, and very strong ranges. There were 52 discordant variants with predictive evidence of deleteriousness, of which 4, 9, 17, and 22 respectively attained PS4-LLR towards benignity in the supporting, moderate, strong, and very strong ranges.

Application of PS4-LLR evidence for classifying VUS and conflicting variants

In total, 90% (3,702/4,111) of VUS and conflicting variants present in our five datasets have PS4-LLR applied towards either pathogenicity or benignity, and of these, 63% (2,339/3,702) have this evidence applied at strong or higher (Table S5). These variants might benefit from quantified case-control evidence to enable classification out of their VUS status.

For the 1,929 VUS or conflicting variants with case-control evidence in *BRCA1* and *BRCA2*, 515 also had functional and/or predictive evidence. To meet the ACMG/AMP v3.0 requirement that classifications are reached using at least two non-contradicting criteria¹, variants were only classified if they had case-control evidence plus either concordant functional data or predictive data.

14 variants (10 in *BRCA1*, 4 in *BRCA2*) attained at least Likely Pathogenic using these evidence items, and 381 (150 in *BRCA1*, 231 in *BRCA2*) variants attained at least Likely Benign. This totalled 74% (381/515) variants which attained sufficient evidence for classification using automated evidence application including quantified case-control data (Table S6).

Reduced penetrance variants in high penetrance genes

We compared PS4-LLR at a target odds of association of OR=4 and OR=2 for *BRCA1*, *BRCA2* and *PALB2* to examine the change in applicable evidence strengths in the context of reduced penetrance.

Of the 2,812 rare missense variants in these three genes, the shift in PS4-LLR when reducing the target odds ratio from 4 to 2 indicated possible reduced penetrance for 357 variants (12.0% (94/783) in *BRCA1*, 12.2% (181/1489) in *BRCA2*, and 15.2% (82/540) in *PALB2* (Figure S3, Table S7, see Methods), of which 66% (235/357) notably already had a conflicting classification in ClinVar.

High penetrance variants in (otherwise) moderate penetrance genes

Finally, we examined the impact of increasing the target odds ratio from 2 to 4 for variants in moderate penetrance genes (*ATM* and *CHEK2*) which had attained at least very strong pathogenic evidence at a target odds of association of 2 (the standard odds ratio for these genes as suggested by the ClinGen HBOP VCEP for *ATM*¹⁹) (Table S8).

37 rare missense variants in *ATM* and *CHEK2* maintained at least strong evidence at this increased target odds ratio of OR=4: 1.5% (21/1,375) in *ATM* and 4.3% (16/376) in *CHEK2*. Notably included in this list was *ATM* c.7271T>G (p.V2424G), a well-established high penetrance variant.

Discussion (2110)

We present here the largest case-control analysis to date involving data from 325,345 breast cancer cases and 671,006 controls, examining PS4-LLR in five genes and generating evidence assisting classification for 6,275 rare variants (4,563 rare missense variants). We focus here on missense variants, as this variant type stands to benefit most towards definitive classification from a more quantitative approach to case-control data. PS4-LLRs are also presented for protein truncating variants (PTVs) (Table S2); the average per-gene evidence towards pathogenicity is greater for protein truncating variants compared to missense (Figure S1), but these variant types tend to achieve classification more readily by virtue of high weight placed on mutational type.

Patterns of PS4-LLR scores across and between genes

57% (6,131/10,694) of missense variants could not be included for PS4-LLR analysis, nearly all due to being singleton observations. Of the 4,563 recurrently-observed analysable variants, overall 20% (922/4,563) of variants received PS4-LLR evidence towards pathogenicity (LLR \geq 1) and 70% (3,188/4,563) received PS4-LLR evidence towards benignity (LLR \leq -1).

Observed differences between the genes in variant numbers will in part reflect inherent characteristics regarding gene length and constraint, as well as the greater volume of testing data for *BRCA1/BRCA2*. A variant will more readily attain evidence towards benignity in the context of application of a higher target OR, meaning that the distribution of benignity scores is accordingly skewed for *BRCA1*, *BRCA2* and *PALB2* compared to *ATM* and *CHEK2*. Furthermore, even amongst our high penetrance genes, although measured against a standardised working clinical definition of high penetrance of OR \geq 4, the magnitude of their underlying association with breast cancer differs quite widely between genes, estimated in a recent large meta-analysis as being OR=8.73 for *BRCA1*, OR=5.68 for *BRCA2* and OR=4.30 for *PALB2*²³. Thus a *BRCA1* missense variant of 'true underlying OR' typical for a *BRCA1* PV will attain stronger PS4-LLR towards pathogenicity than a *BRCA2* missense variant of 'true underlying OR' typical for *BRCA2* PV when both are measured against a target OR \geq 4. Consistent with this, we observed for *BRCA1* a higher proportion of variants attaining points towards pathogenicity and a higher proportion attaining strong/very strong than *BRCA2*. Also consistent with this we observed a lower proportion of *PALB2* variants attaining strong/very strong PS4-LLR towards pathogenicity (although it has also been posited from other analyses that very few *PALB2* missense variants are pathogenic)¹⁸. While we present PS4-LLR

calculated using $OR \geq 4$ to align with current standard clinical classification practice for these genes, we also present as a comparison PS4-LLR calculated using bespoke target odds for each gene (as estimated from the recent meta-analysis (Table S12)).

Variant frequency also influences scores owing to increased power. The *BRCA1* variant c.1487G>A (p.R496H) illustrates attainment of a sizeable benignity score of -1016 (Table S2) through combination of a comparatively high variant frequency (being of allele frequency of 0.00081 in gnomAD v4.1 and observed 691 times in controls in UKB, only just passing the rarity threshold for inclusion of ≥ 0.00086) and the higher target odds ratio used for *BRCA1* compared to *ATM/CHEK2*. Variant frequency (power) likewise boosted pathogenicity scores for some highly recurrent variants, such as *BRCA1*: c.181T>G (p.C61G) (+161), *BRCA2*: c.7988A>T (p.E2663V) (+136) and c.8167G>C (p.D2723H) (+120).

For the moderate penetrance genes *CHEK2* and *ATM*, the underlying odds ratio is more similar to the operational target odds ratio of 2, being estimated in recent meta-analysis as being 2.17 for *ATM* and 2.44 for *CHEK2*²³. While a lower proportion of *ATM* missense variants attained the highest category of PS4-LLR score (very strong), and the mean score among all scored variants in *ATM* was lower than for *CHEK2* (-6.2 versus -2.5), the range of scores for *ATM* was much broader than for *CHEK2* (Figure 2). This likely reflects inclusion of some more recurrent high-scoring variants such as *ATM*: c.6919C>T (p.L2307F) (+104) and c.7271T>G (p.V2424G) (+65). Interestingly, whilst *ATM* c.7271T>G (p.V2424G) is a known high-penetrance pathogenic variant, *ATM* c.6919C>T (p.L2307F) has previously been classified as being benign on the basis of its high frequency in the Ashkenazi Jewish (AJ) population in gnomAD v2.1.1; this sizeable case-control signal would suggest a possible founder effect in the AJ population rather than neutrality of the variant, and indeed this variant has previously been associated with other cancers in AJ populations²⁴⁻²⁶.

Inclusion of enriched clinical datasets: adjustment and utility

We illustrate for the first time combination of enriched datasets with unselected datasets to generate an integrated likelihood ratio scoring. Notably the NDRS-UK laboratory data were more enriched for PTVs in *BRCA1* and *BRCA2* compared to the Ambry dataset, reflecting the stricter criteria for testing eligibility. It was also interesting to note the different enrichment factors by gene, which are a predictable reflection of how subtype-specific breast cancer association varies by gene. This, along with differences in the case make-up of datasets due to eligibility for diagnostic testing (for example, disproportionate inclusion of triple-negative breast cancers), are consistent with the higher enrichment factor for *BRCA1*.

Inclusion of the Ambry-US and NDRS-UK diagnostic laboratory datasets greatly increased power, adding an additional 232,559 enriched breast cancer cases to the 92,786 available from the three unselected series, and resulting in potentially applicable evidence for 4,563 missense variants, compared with 926 available missense variants if using case-control data from only the three unselected datasets using a meta-analysis (Table 3, Table S9).

Concordance of PS4-LLR scores with other data sources

Overall concordance against previously classified missense variants in ClinVar for all genes was relatively high, with 72% (84/116) P/LP ClinVar classified variants attaining $PS4-LLR \geq 1$ (evidence towards pathogenicity), and 89% (190/214) of B/LB ClinVar classified variants attaining $PS4-LLR \leq -1$ (evidence towards benignity). Concordance was modestly higher when restricting to 2* classifications (80% and 90% for $PS4-LLR$ towards pathogenicity and benignity respectively). Notably, very few *ATM*, *CHEK2* or *PALB2* missense variants attained 1* or higher ClinVar classifications, meaning assessment of concordance was mostly based on *BRCA1* and *BRCA2* ClinVar classifications.

Where discordant with ClinVar, typically variants only attained supporting or moderate PS4-LLR evidence in the discordant direction. Some discordant data is expected between ClinVar and PS4-LLR evidence as PS4-LLR represents a single evidence component, while ClinVar classifications incorporate the full spectrum of applicable evidence, and additionally PS4-LLR is impacted by low and stochastic frequency in case datasets. However, one plausible explanation for a proportion of the discordancies will be variants being of reduced penetrance, meaning these variants attain PS4-LLR evidence towards benignity when assessed against a high penetrance target OR (Table S13). Notably for PTVs, 61 *BRCA1*, *BRCA2*, and *PALB2* variants with a pathogenic/likely pathogenic ClinVar classification attained at least strong benign evidence at $OR \geq 4$, including suspected reduced penetrance variant *BRCA2* c.8331+2T>C (Table S13). It should be noted that these data do not account for variability in genotype-phenotype associations (for example a *BRCA1* variant conferring hypothetical “ovarian-predominant, breast-minimal” risk). As such, the PS4-LLR variant evidence presented is a reflection only on breast cancer risk.

Although majority concordant with functional and in silico predictions, discordancies with these data may again highlight reduced (or alternative) penetrance. Furthermore, functional and in silico data types are not ‘gold-standards’ for classification status. Functional classifications, as per the Brnich guidance, are assigned dichotomously, meaning that some variants assigned as functionally deleterious may exhibit weaker assay scores and lie very near to the assigned threshold for deleteriousness. In silico tools are widely recognised to over-predict deleteriousness, which was consistent with the pattern we observed in our discordancies.^{5,27,28}

Using PS4-LLRs to identify variants of atypical penetrance

Our existing clinical approaches to variant classification are based on a simplistic assumption that the variant will be either “fully penetrant” (in quasi-Mendelian fashion) or have no association with disease. We are as a community recognising an urgent requirement for new approaches to identification and classification of variants of reduced penetrance, not least as these will require different clinical management.

Analysing all variants in high penetrance genes *BRCA1*, *BRCA2* and *PALB2* against both a target odds ratio of 4 (high penetrance) and 2 (moderate penetrance), we were able to flag 357 variants as being of putatively-reduced penetrance, 235 of which also had a conflicting classification in ClinVar. These included *BRCA2* c.520C>T p.(Leu174Phe), previously reported as reduced penetrance in the UK¹⁰, and *BRCA2* c.9302T>G (p.L3101R), a variant previously asserted as being of reduced penetrance based on a cancer family history algorithm³¹ and flagged in our analysis as being putatively of reduced penetrance when comparing to the *BRCA2*-specific effect size estimate of 5.68 (Table S12). However, this analysis did not identify all known reduced penetrance missense variants; interestingly, *BRCA1* c.5096G>A (p.R1699Q)³², proposed and clinically-managed as reduced penetrance on the basis of segregation analyses, retained strong scoring for benignity against target ORs of either 4 or 2. This was driven by complete absence of the variant in breast cancer cases in BRIDGES and UK Biobank. On previous case-control analysis of this variant in unselected datasets, an odds ratio towards benignity was likewise reported, indicating this to be a product of the constituent datasets rather than methodology⁵.

We also identified 37 variants in moderate penetrance genes that are putatively of high penetrance: these included the one well-established exemplar variant of this class *ATM* c.7271T>G (p.V2424G), which has long been recognised to be of atypically high penetrance and is managed clinically as per a *BRCA1/BRCA2* variant³³.

Limitations

To avoid stratification due to population structure we restricted our analyses to the white-only subsets of these datasets. With growing availability of additional datasets containing sizeable numbers of non-white participants such as AllOfUs, application of this methodology may generate PS4-LLR scores for additional variants for which allele frequencies are higher in non-white ancestry groups.

A feature of the PS4-LLR methodology is that when variants have well-powered association signals lying between $OR=1$ and the target OR , the likelihood areas for ratio comparison can be excessively small precluding robust analysis: for these reasons a handful of relatively frequent alleles well-established as having lower-penetrance breast cancer association will not be included in this analysis, such as *CHEK2* c.470T>C (p.I157T)³⁴ (Table S14).

For BRIDGES and CARRIERS, the control series were female only. In order to optimise the case-control balance for matching of controls to the clinical series, it was necessary to retain male samples in the control series of UK Biobank and gnomAD v4.1.0. In principle, this might potentially have resulted in a very small degree of attenuation of the case-control signal, which would serve only to dampen very slightly the LLR towards pathogenicity.

For the NDRS-UK diagnostic laboratory data, laboratories only submitted rare variants classified internally as VUS, pathogenic or likely pathogenic. Because variants were not submitted by the laboratories if presumptively benign, the case counts for some variants may be under-represented. Thus, we excluded evidence attained towards benignity from this dataset. Additionally, we acknowledge that heterogeneity in variant calling methods between datasets means absence of a variant in a dataset may reflect lower coverage of that region in that dataset. For both of these reasons which reduce the number of informative datasets contributing to PS4-LLR, we recognise that the scoring towards pathogenicity may have been conservative, underscoring some of the caveats of using multi-centre real-world healthcare data.

We only examined data for five breast cancer susceptibility genes, and only considered the two 'clinically-actionable' thresholds for effect sizes. It will be of value to explore application of the likelihood ratio methodology to a broader range of gene-disease paradigms, for example exploring rare disease scenarios in which a much higher effect size would be anticipated (ie $OR=100$ or $OR=1000$). Quantitative harnessing of case-control data is important not only for generation of direct evidence for variant interpretation, but can afford accurate calibration and validation of new functional assays and computational prediction tools.

Conclusion

These data illustrate the utility and flexibility of the PS4-likelihood ratio methodology in conjunction with the enhanced power afforded from integrating large enriched clinical datasets with unselected case-control datasets. This enabled analysis of 13,829 rare variants in total, including 10,694 missense variants, generating evidence for classification for 6,275 variants overall and 4,563 missense variants across five breast cancer predisposition genes widely tested clinically. We illustrate generation of case-control evidence towards classification of benignity, which is integral to the forthcoming v4.0 revision to the ClinGen ACMG variant classification framework (having previously only allowed case-control evidence towards pathogenicity). We demonstrate the versatility of this tool for quantitative assessment of association against different target odds ratios, allowing evaluation of variants in both high penetrance genes and moderate penetrance genes, as well as for identification of variants of atypical penetrance. These approaches will become increasingly important as there is

increasing recognition within variant interpretation of the importance of accounting for variable penetrance.

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Author contribution

Conceptualisation: CT; Submission of raw data to NDRS: CanVIG-UK; Data Curation: FC, MR, TP, JP, KL, FM, SV, SH, BT, LL; Development of the PS4-LR-Calculator: CFR, CL, NW, MJ; Formal Analysis: SA, CFR; Funding acquisition: CT; Investigation: SA; Methodology: CT, SA, CFR, AG; Project Administration: SA, Supervision: CT; Visualisation: SA; Validation: MD, GJB, AC, RR, JF, BF, SPS, JG, JP, TMcD, KS, HH, TMcV, CanVIG-UK; Writing – original draft: CT, SA; Writing - review and editing: all authors.

Data availability

UK Biobank data used in these analyses are available from UK Biobank upon request (<https://www.ukbiobank.ac.uk>). Summary data used from the BRIDGES consortium is available at the following link: <https://www.ccge.medschl.cam.ac.uk/breast-cancer-association-consortium-bcac/data-data-access/summary-results/bridges-summary-results>. Data access for CARRIERS, NDRS, and Ambry data was attained on request and is subject to application and project approval from the respective team leads. All other secondary data relevant to the study are included in the article or are uploaded as supplementary information.

Code availability

Scripts used to generate the results in this manuscript are available on request.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors declare the following competing interests: MER and TP are employees of Ambry Genetics and equity shareholders of Tempus AI. AG reports honoraria for educational webinars from AstraZeneca and Diaceutics.

References

1. Richards, S., Aziz, N., Bale, S., Bick, D., Das, S., Gastier-Foster, J., Grody, W.W., Hegde, M., Lyon, E., Spector, E., et al. (2015). Standards and guidelines for the interpretation of sequence variants: a joint consensus recommendation of the American College of Medical Genetics and Genomics and the Association for Molecular Pathology. *Genetics in medicine : official journal of the American College of Medical Genetics* 17, 405-424. 10.1038/gim.2015.30.
2. Tavigian, S.V., Greenblatt, M.S., Harrison, S.M., Nussbaum, R.L., Prabhu, S.A., Boucher, K.M., and Biesecker, L.G. (2018). Modeling the ACMG/AMP variant classification guidelines as a Bayesian classification framework. *Genetics in medicine : official journal of the American College of Medical Genetics* 20, 1054-1060. 10.1038/gim.2017.210.
3. Rowlands, C.F., Garrett, A., Allen, S., Durkie, M., Burghel, G.J., Robinson, R., Callaway, A., Field, J., Frugtinet, B., Palmer-Smith, S., et al. (2024). The PS4-likelihood ratio calculator: flexible allocation of evidence weighting for case-control data in variant classification. *Journal of medical genetics*. 10.1136/jmg-2024-110034.
4. Tavigian, S.V., Harrison, S.M., Boucher, K.M., and Biesecker, L.G. (2020). Fitting a naturally scaled point system to the ACMG/AMP variant classification guidelines. *Human mutation*. 10.1002/humu.24088.
5. Zanti, M., O'Mahony, D.G., Parsons, M.T., Dorling, L., Dennis, J., Boddicker, N.J., Chen, W., Hu, C., Naven, M., Yiangou, K., et al. (2024). Analysis of more than 400,000 women provides case-control evidence for BRCA1 and BRCA2 variant classification. 10.1101/2024.09.04.24313051.
6. Dorling, L., Carvalho, S., Allen, J., González-Neira, A., Luccarini, C., Wahlström, C., Pooley, K.A., Parsons, M.T., Fortunato, C., Wang, Q., et al. (2021). Breast Cancer Risk Genes - Association Analysis in More than 113,000 Women. *The New England journal of medicine* 384, 428-439. 10.1056/NEJMoa1913948.
7. Hu, C., Hart, S.N., Gnanaolivu, R., Huang, H., Lee, K.Y., Na, J., Gao, C., Lilyquist, J., Yadav, S., Boddicker, N.J., et al. (2021). A Population-Based Study of Genes Previously Implicated in Breast Cancer. *The New England journal of medicine* 384, 440-451. 10.1056/NEJMoa2005936.
8. Bycroft, C., Freeman, C., Petkova, D., Band, G., Elliott, L.T., Sharp, K., Motyer, A., Vukcevic, D., Delaneau, O., O'Connell, J., et al. (2018). The UK Biobank resource with deep phenotyping and genomic data. *Nature* 562, 203-209. 10.1038/s41586-018-0579-z.
9. Moghadasi, S., Meeks, H.D., Vreeswijk, M.P., Janssen, L.A., Borg, A., Ehrencrona, H., Paulsson-Karlsson, Y., Wappenschmidt, B., Engel, C., Gehrig, A., et al. (2018). The BRCA1 c. 5096G>A p.Arg1699Gln (R1699Q) intermediate risk variant: breast and ovarian cancer risk estimation and recommendations for clinical management from the ENIGMA consortium. *Journal of medical genetics* 55, 15-20. 10.1136/jmedgenet-2017-104560.
10. Garrett, A., Allen, S., Durkie, M., Burghel, G.J., Robinson, R., Callaway, A., Field, J., Frugtinet, B., Palmer-Smith, S., Grant, J., et al. (2025). Classification of variants of reduced penetrance in high-penetrance cancer susceptibility genes: Framework for genetics clinicians and clinical scientists by CanVIG-UK (Cancer Variant Interpretation

- Group-UK). *Genetics in medicine : official journal of the American College of Medical Genetics* 27, 101305. 10.1016/j.gim.2024.101305.
11. Mukhtar, T.K., Wilcox, N., Dennis, J., Yang, X., Naven, M., Mavaddat, N., Perry, J.R.B., Gardner, E., and Easton, D.F. (2024). Protein-truncating and rare missense variants in ATM and CHEK2 and associations with cancer in UK Biobank whole-exome sequence data. *Journal of medical genetics* 61, 1016-1022. 10.1136/jmg-2024-110127.
 12. Spurdle, A.B., Greville-Heygate, S., Antoniou, A.C., Brown, M., Burke, L., de la Hoya, M., Domchek, S., Dork, T., Firth, H.V., Monteiro, A.N., et al. (2019). Towards controlled terminology for reporting germline cancer susceptibility variants: an ENIGMA report. *Journal of medical genetics* 56, 347-357. 10.1136/jmedgenet-2018-105872.
 13. Parsons, M.T., de la Hoya, M., Richardson, M.E., Tudini, E., Anderson, M., Berkofsky-Fessler, W., Caputo, S.M., Chan, R.C., Cline, M.S., Feng, B.J., et al. (2024). Evidence-based recommendations for gene-specific ACMG/AMP variant classification from the ClinGen ENIGMA BRCA1 and BRCA2 Variant Curation Expert Panel. *American journal of human genetics*. 10.1016/j.ajhg.2024.07.013.
 14. Karczewski, K.J., Francioli, L.C., Tiao, G., Cummings, B.B., Alföldi, J., Wang, Q., Collins, R.L., Laricchia, K.M., Ganna, A., Birnbaum, D.P., et al. (2020). The mutational constraint spectrum quantified from variation in 141,456 humans. *Nature* 581, 434-443. 10.1038/s41586-020-2308-7.
 15. McLaren, W., Gil, L., Hunt, S.E., Riat, H.S., Ritchie, G.R., Thormann, A., Flicek, P., and Cunningham, F. (2016). The Ensembl Variant Effect Predictor. *Genome biology* 17, 122. 10.1186/s13059-016-0974-4.
 16. Freeman, P.J., Hart, R.K., Gretton, L.J., Brookes, A.J., and Dalgleish, R. (2018). VariantValidator: Accurate validation, mapping, and formatting of sequence variation descriptions. *Human mutation* 39, 61-68. 10.1002/humu.23348.
 17. Freeman, P.J., Wagstaff, J.F., Fokkema, I., Cutting, G.R., Rehm, H.L., Davies, A.C., den Dunnen, J.T., Gretton, L.J., and Dalgleish, R. (2024). Standardizing variant naming in literature with VariantValidator to increase diagnostic rates. *Nature genetics* 56, 2284-2286. 10.1038/s41588-024-01938-w.
 18. Richardson, M.E., Bishop, M.F.H., Holdren, M.A., de la Hoya, M., Spurdle, A.B., Tavtigian, S.V., Brannan, T., Young, C.C., Zec, L., Hiraki, S., et al. (2025). Specifications of the ACMG/AMP variant curation guidelines for the analysis of germline PALB2 sequence variants. *American journal of human genetics*. 10.1016/j.ajhg.2025.08.020.
 19. Richardson, M.E., Holdren, M., Brannan, T., de la Hoya, M., Spurdle, A.B., Tavtigian, S.V., Young, C.C., Zec, L., Hiraki, S., Anderson, M.J., et al. (2024). Specifications of the ACMG/AMP variant curation guidelines for the analysis of germline ATM sequence variants. *American journal of human genetics* 111, 2411-2426. 10.1016/j.ajhg.2024.08.022.
 20. Landrum, M.J., Lee, J.M., Riley, G.R., Jang, W., Rubinstein, W.S., Church, D.M., and Maglott, D.R. (2014). ClinVar: public archive of relationships among sequence variation and human phenotype. *Nucleic acids research* 42, D980-985. 10.1093/nar/gkt1113.
 21. Feng, B.-J. (2017). PERCH: A Unified Framework for Disease Gene Prioritization. *Human mutation* 38, 243-251. 10.1002/humu.23158.
 22. Jaganathan, K., Kyriazopoulou Panagiotopoulou, S., McRae, J.F., Darbandi, S.F., Knowles, D., Li, Y.I., Kosmicki, J.A., Arbelaez, J., Cui, W., Schwartz, G.B., et al. (2019). Predicting Splicing from Primary Sequence with Deep Learning. *Cell* 176, 535-548 e524. 10.1016/j.cell.2018.12.015.
 23. Rowlands, C.F., Allen, S., Balmaña, J., Domchek, S.M., Evans, D.G., Hanson, H., Hoogerbrugge, N., James, P.A., Nathanson, K., Robson, M., et al. (2024). Population-based germline breast cancer gene association studies and meta-analysis to inform wider mainstream testing. *Ann Oncol*. 10.1016/j.annonc.2024.07.244.

24. Lampson, B.L., Gupta, A., Tyekucheveva, S., Mashima, K., Petrackova, A., Wang, Z., Wojciechowska, N., Shaughnessy, C.J., Baker, P.O., Fernandes, S.M., et al. (2023). Rare Germline ATM Variants Influence the Development of Chronic Lymphocytic Leukemia. *Journal of clinical oncology : official journal of the American Society of Clinical Oncology* *41*, 1116-1128. 10.1200/JCO.22.00269.
25. Ji, X., Mukherjee, S., Landi, M.T., Bosse, Y., Joubert, P., Zhu, D., Gorlov, I., Xiao, X., Han, Y., Gorlova, O., et al. (2020). Protein-altering germline mutations implicate novel genes related to lung cancer development. *Nature communications* *11*, 2220. 10.1038/s41467-020-15905-6.
26. Borsani, O., Jager, R., Pietra, D., Flieder, I., Riccaboni, G., Kralovics, R., and Rumi, E. (2024). Evaluation of the ATM L2307F germline variant in 121 Italian pedigrees with familial myeloproliferative neoplasms. *Haematologica* *109*, 2738-2740. 10.3324/haematol.2024.285539.
27. Pejaver, V., Byrne, A.B., Feng, B.J., Pagel, K.A., Mooney, S.D., Karchin, R., O'Donnell-Luria, A., Harrison, S.M., Tavtigian, S.V., Greenblatt, M.S., et al. (2022). Calibration of computational tools for missense variant pathogenicity classification and ClinGen recommendations for PP3/BP4 criteria. *American journal of human genetics* *109*, 2163-2177. 10.1016/j.ajhg.2022.10.013.
28. Cubuk, C., Garrett, A., Choi, S., King, L., Loveday, C., Torr, B., Burghel, G.J., Durkie, M., Callaway, A., Robinson, R., et al. (2021). Clinical likelihood ratios and balanced accuracy for 44 in silico tools against multiple large-scale functional assays of cancer susceptibility genes. *Genetics in medicine : official journal of the American College of Medical Genetics*. 10.1038/s41436-021-01265-z.
29. Wright, C.F., Sharp, L.N., Jackson, L., Murray, A., Ware, J.S., MacArthur, D.G., Rehm, H.L., Patel, K.A., and Weedon, M.N. (2024). Guidance for estimating penetrance of monogenic disease-causing variants in population cohorts. *Nature genetics* *56*, 1772-1779. 10.1038/s41588-024-01842-3.
30. Wright, C.F., West, B., Tuke, M., Jones, S.E., Patel, K., Laver, T.W., Beaumont, R.N., Tyrrell, J., Wood, A.R., Frayling, T.M., et al. (2019). Assessing the Pathogenicity, Penetrance, and Expressivity of Putative Disease-Causing Variants in a Population Setting. *American journal of human genetics* *104*, 275-286. 10.1016/j.ajhg.2018.12.015.
31. Pal, T., Mundt, E., Richardson, M.E., Chao, E., Pesaran, T., Slavin, T.P., Couch, F.J., and Monteiro, A.N.A. (2024). Reduced penetrance BRCA1 and BRCA2 pathogenic variants in clinical germline genetic testing. *NPJ Precis Oncol* *8*, 247. 10.1038/s41698-024-00741-4.
32. Moghadasi, S., Meeks, H.D., Vreeswijk, M.P., Janssen, L.A., Borg, A., Ehrencrona, H., Paulsson-Karlsson, Y., Wappenschmidt, B., Engel, C., Gehrig, A., et al. (2017). The BRCA1 c. 5096G>A p.Arg1699Gln (R1699Q) intermediate risk variant: breast and ovarian cancer risk estimation and recommendations for clinical management from the ENIGMA consortium. *Journal of medical genetics*. 10.1136/jmedgenet-2017-104560.
33. Bernstein, J.L., Teraoka, S., Southey, M.C., Jenkins, M.A., Andrulis, I.L., Knight, J.A., John, E.M., Lapinski, R., Wolitzer, A.L., Whittemore, A.S., et al. (2006). Population-based estimates of breast cancer risks associated with ATM gene variants c.7271T>G and c.1066-6T>G (IVS10-6T>G) from the Breast Cancer Family Registry. *Human mutation* *27*, 1122-1128. 10.1002/humu.20415.
34. Han, F.F., Guo, C.L., and Liu, L.H. (2013). The effect of CHEK2 variant I157T on cancer susceptibility: evidence from a meta-analysis. *DNA and cell biology* *32*, 329-335. 10.1089/dna.2013.1970.